

Shaping international standards for advanced technologies

INSTAR is a European funded Coordination and Support Action funded under the Horizon Europe Programme of the European Commission that aims to shape international standards in key emerging technologies by collaborating with relevant entities from Australia, Canada, Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan and the USA.

What are the European Task Forces (ETFs)?

The INSTAR ETFs are groups of European standardisation and domain experts who are actively contributing to innovate the **AI, Cybersecurity, Digital ID, IoT, 5G, 6G, Quantum Technologies**, and **Data Technologies** domains.

ETFs Roadmap

The INSTAR roadmaps serve as strategic frameworks that identify and align the EU's priorities with those of international partners, creating actionable pathways to influence global ICT standardisation. Aligning on international standardisation roadmaps is critical for Europe to ensure its priorities are reflected in global standards, paving the way to more innovation and increased competitiveness. These roadmaps are specifically designed to engage experts from standardisation bodies, policymakers, and industries, providing a common platform to guide collaboration, harmonise objectives, and shape the future of global ICT standards. This proactive approach allows Europe to lead and remain a key player in the development of standards that underpin technology adoption, interoperability, and fair market conditions on a global scale.

5G+/6G Roadmap

The priorities listed in this fact sheet reflect the current state of discussions. The priorities will be continuously updated throughout the project.

5G+/6G Standardisation Priorities

- Identify Beyond 5G/6G standardisation gaps and priorities to support existing EU legislation and standardisation priorities in collaboration with international partners from Australia, Canada, Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan & the US.
- Contribute towards the INSTAR Standards Tracer with a 6G knowledge area to SDO mapping.
- Define a roadmap with recommendations towards harmonisation of international standards, and 6G knowledge.
- Seek opportunities for cooperation and knowledge sharing with other countries to accelerate 6G development and deployment.

How to contribute to the ETFs

To contribute to INSTAR's goals and our European Task Forces, subscribe to our newsletter and make sure to follow both our LinkedIn and X accounts to stay updated on the ETFs next steps and input requests!

Learn more
about the ETFs

Our consortium

